

THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATUS OF LIVESTOCK FARMERS: A MICRO LEVEL STUDY OF DONAJ VILLAGE IN MANGALWEDHA TAHSIL OF SOLAPUR DISTRICT (MS)

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ABSTRACT

The prime objective of this research is to study and examine the socio economic status of livestock farmers in Donaj village. This study conducted following exploratory research design to ascertain the profile characteristics of livestock farmers. This study was conducted in Donaj which is in Mangalwedha tahsil of Solapur district. For this purpose 150 livestock farmers of this village were selected. Questionnaires were used to collect data from livestock farmer. In this study region the majority of the peoples are landless and small land holder. In this village majority of people do not have land for grazing animal which they depend on others field.

Some people in this region are low income group, less consumption of milk, less production of milk and low income source. 66.67 percent of respondents were taking fruit crops in this region. Which are cash crops but this is not useful for cattle. If people use their scientific method for raring animals they will improve their socio-economic status.

KEY WORDS: GDP, food security, sustainable development, revolution, biodiversity

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture, with its allied sectors, is unquestionably the largest livelihood provider in India, more so in the vast rural areas. It also contributes a significant figure to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Sustainable agriculture, in terms of food security, rural employment and environmentally sustainable technologies such as soil conservation, sustainable natural resource management and biodiversity protection are essential for holistic rural development. Indian agriculture and allied activities have witnessed a green revolution, a white revolution, a yellow revolution and a blue revolution.

Agriculture plays a vital role in the Indian economy. Over 70 percent of the rural households depend on agriculture as their principal means of livelihood. The total share of Agriculture and allied sectors in terms of percentage of GDP is 13.9 percent during 2013-14. A large number of farmers in India depend on animal husbandry for their livelihood. Thus animal husbandry plays an important role in the rural economy. The dairy subsector occupied an important position in agriculture economy of India, as milk is the second largest agriculture commodity. In India, the dairy sector provide regular employment of many people in rural India. Many people are engaged in this country for production of milk, therefore a large number of unemployed persons have got employment due to this sector. Donaj is one of the important village in Mangalwedha tahsil of Solapur district (MS). Agriculture is major

economic activities in this village. But some due to lack of water availability they find some difficulty in production of agriculture commodities. One of the challenges in this village to generate the self-employment opportunity which will be based on their agriculture and milk production is the best option to this which will help to generate job opportunity as well as self-employment by dairying. But some time they faced some problems in this sector. Present investigation is carried out to analyze the socio-economic status of the livestock farmers in the study region.

OBJECTIVES

Some of the specific objectives of the study are as follows.

1. To find out the socio-economic status of livestock farmers in Donaj Village.
2. To examine the role of animal husbandry in rural economy.

STUDY REGION

Donaj is one of the important villages in Mangalwedha taluka in Solapur district of Maharashtra state, India. It belongs to the Desh of Pachim Maharashtra region. It belongs to Pune division. Donaj village is bounded by $17^{\circ}26'21.74''$ N to $17^{\circ}28'17.72''$ N latitudes and $75^{\circ}31'35.50''$ E to $75^{\circ}34'38.79''$ E longitudes. It is located 59 km from the district head quarter of Solapur and 16 km from Mangalwedha. It is 499 meters above mean sea level.

Map 1

Location Map of Study Region

DATABASE AND METHODOLOGY

The present study was based on primary as well as secondary data. The primary data were collected through the questionnaires. For this purpose 150 respondents were selected randomly from the livestock farmers in the Donaj village. Data were also collected from secondary sources of information as like official documents such as records, registers and reports in Grampanchat office which were taken by the Talathi and Gramsevak.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**1. Land holding category of livestock farmers**

It could be observed from Table No.1, 50 percent of farmers are medium land holders. The landless farmers also found in this village which is low percent but it shows dangerous situation for the peoples, because the daily routine is difficult. Some peoples are engaged in the agriculture worker in the others field.

Table 1
Category of farmers according to land holding

Sr. No.	Category	No of Farmers	Percentage (%)
1	Landless farmers	24	16.00
2	Marginal Land	51	34.00
3	Medium Land	75	50.00
4	Total	150	100.00

2. Personal, Socio-Economic characteristics of Livestock Farmers

The following table indicates that the more than half percent (62) of the respondent's income is low, because in this village agriculture is major source for income and the major of peoples are agriculture worker. High income agriculture farmers are less than the other low and medium income farmers.

Further it was found the given table that the 88.67 percent livestock farmers are in the nuclear family, the limited people are also found joint family which indicates the traditional societies plays vital role for this situation. In this village $\frac{3}{4}$ livestock farmers are small family size which indicates the high literacy. Other hand nearly 5.67 percent of livestock farmers in large family which family members are more than 7 peoples.

In this village more than 80 percent of peoples are males which are the decision taker for family. 14 percent females also take the decision for family which also indicate changing trend towards the females. 1.34 percent are livestock farmers, which take decision together.

Table 2
Personal, Socio Economic Characteristics of Livestock farmers

Sr. No.	Characteristics	Distribution	Percentage
1	Income	Low	62.00
		Medium	26.00
		High	12.00
2	Family Type	Nuclear Family	88.67
		Joint Family	11.33
3	Family Size	Small (1-4)	75.00
		Medium(4-7)	19.33
		Large(>7)	5.67
4	Decision Maker of the family	Men	84.66
		Women	14.00
		Together	1.34

3. Land Holding and Cropping Pattern of Livestock farmers

In the table no.3, majority (64.67) of the respondents were holding small acres of rainfed land followed by medium (27.99) and large (7.34). Similarly, majority (79.33) of the livestock farmers had small irrigated land holding and 17.33 percentage of livestock farmers had medium and only 3.34 percentage of livestock farmers had large irrigated land holding.

It was revealed from the table No.3, majority of the respondents (40.69) were growing sugarcane followed by grapes (23.99), Jowar (13.34), Horsegram (5.34), Banana (4.67), Neem (3.99). It is clear that the cash crops are the major crops in this village. This is useful for the income source.

Table 3
Land Holding and Cropping Pattern of Livestock farmers

Sr. No	Categories	Distribution	Percentage
1	Rainfed Land holding	Small(0-5) Acres	64.67
		Medium (5-10) Acres	27.99
		Large (>10) Acres	7.34
2	Irrigated land holding	Small (0-2)	79.33
		Medium(2-5)	17.33
		Large(>5)	3.34
3	Types of Crops grown	Sugarcane	40.69
		Grapes	23.99
		Jowar	13.34
		Neem	3.99
		Horsegram	5.34
		Banana	4.67
		Pomegranate	1.99
		Others	5.99

4. Types of livestock

Due to lack of work, many peoples are engaged in the livestock possession for milk production. The following diagram shows that majority of respondents are possessed indigenous breed (30%), followed by Crossbred cattle (28%), Buffaloes (19%), Goat (14%) and Sheep (9%). The high percent of people get the wattages for milk production. So landless respondents are difficult to manage the livestock without the availability of grazing land and fodder.

5. Milk Production details of livestock

The following table shows that low (below 10 liter) milk production is high level (61.16), followed by medium (29.79) and high (9.05). Also the consumption of milk is low in this village and sale of milk also found low (below 2 liter). The above table indicates that the high livestock farmers are engaged in the production of milk but the consumption is very low because they want to the sale the milk for the income source.

Table No.4
Milk Production Details of livestock

Sr. No.	Details	Categories(in Liter)	Percentage
1	Milk Production	Low (0 – 10)	61.16
		Medium (10 – 20)	29.79
		High (> 20)	9.05
2	Milk Consumption	Low (0 – 2.5)	49.56
		Medium (2.5 – 5)	38.79
		High (> 5)	11.65
3	Sale	Low (0 – 2)	51.11
		Medium (2 – 4)	33.84
		High (> 4)	15.05

CONCLUSION

The availability of land is major source of grazing land and fodder. So majority of people in this region use the some crops for food of animal. From the present investigation it has been concluded that the majority of people are take the fruit crops in their field. So it is not possible to use the food for animals in this region, which farmers faced that was availability of green fodder for their cattle's. Due to non availability of green fodder it becomes difficult to reared dairy animals. Farmers did not get any scientific knowledge or they did not want to take because they did not rear dairy animal as main money generating

source. So it is today's need to aware livestock farmers of this region to rear dairy animal, provide scientific knowledge of livestock and start dairying as a main money generating source therefore it will help to increase their socio-economic status. It is difficult that the change the cropping pattern which will be helpful for their cattle's food.

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